

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Galatan**FIRST NAME:** Bogdan**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 6**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: no plagiarism detected

The author used the following software: MS Word on Office 365

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Where does a quote end when using the Turabian style in writing a dissertation?
 - The period is inside the curly quotation marks.¹**
 - The period is outside the quotation marks.
 - No period is necessary since the curly quotation marks play the role of sentence-ending punctuation.
 - None of the above.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 5th ed.* (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 23.

2. In the context of the European Union, Primary Legislation refers to:
- The series of treaties and agreements with similar status that together constitute the *primary legislation*.**²
 - Legislation that applies in Brussels only.
 - Legislation that governs preliminary elections is called primary.
 - Legislation that is derived from EU secondary and tertiary legislation is based on the legislation from each country.
3. From the options below, what is the correct footnote referencing format when using the Turabian style guide:
- John Perkins, *Understanding Assessment* (London: Penguin, 2008), 78.**³
 - John Perkins. *Understanding Assessment*. (London Penguin, 2008), 78.
 - John Perkins, *Understanding Assessment*. (*London Penguin, 2008, 78*).
 - John Perkins (Understanding Assessment, London, Penguin, 2008, 78)*.
4. Select the correct order of the elements when using the works cited for a book:
- Book Title. Place of Publication. Authors Name. Date. Publisher.
 - Authors Name. Book Title. Date. Publisher. Place of Publication.
 - Authors Name. Date. Book Title. Place of Publication: Publisher.**⁴
 - Publisher. Place of Publication. Authors Name. Book Title. Publisher.

²European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission* (European Commission, 2021), 72.

³Cleenewerck and Gulma, 39.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 38.

5. From the list below, select the incorrect component of dissertation research:
- Dissertation concept paper.
 - Dissertation style and punctuation.**⁵
 - Dissertation prospectus.
 - Dissertation manuscript.
6. Select the correct in-text citation from the options below:
- “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports” (Gerson and Gerson 143).**⁶
 - “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports.” (Gerson and Gerson 143).
 - “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports.” (Gerson and Gerson 143).
 - “Before 1984, footnotes and endnotes were used in research reports” (*Gerson and Gerson 143*).
7. Select the feature of qualitative research that does not belong to the list:
- Qualitative research involves an interpretive naturalistic approach to the world.

⁵ Sampson James P., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research* (Tallahassee: Florida State University Press, 2017), 9.

⁶ Cleenewerck Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 35.

Qualitative research is to examine the numbers and data that support the research findings.⁷

Qualitative research is characterized generally by thick description by thoroughly describing the study's setting.

Qualitative research is grounded in a philosophical position that is essentially constructivist.

8. Select the statement that is incorrect about study limitations:

Limitations of the study expose the conditions that may weaken the study.

Acknowledgment of study limitations is an opportunity to make suggestions for further research.

Limiting the study is a subjective process because you must evaluate the impact of the limitations.

There are studies that do not need certain limitations.⁸

9. What is plagiarism?

Plagiarism is using your own words to express an idea and giving credit to the source.

Plagiarism is giving credit to the source used while using direct quotes.

⁷ Bloomberg Linda Dale and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 144.

⁸ Ibid., 480.

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.⁹**
- Plagiarism is a form of paraphrasing or summarizing while giving credit to the source.

10. Identify from the list below the sentence that indicates the use of American English punctuation:

- “The boy kicked the ball.”¹⁰**
- ‘The boy kicked the ball.’
- ‘The boy kicked the ball.’
- “‘The boy kicked the ball’”.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

¹⁰ Ibid., 31.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. European Commission, 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.